

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

METAPHOR AS A FIGURATIVE DEVICE AND ITS MAIN TYPES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The article investigates some types of metaphors. The article writes that metaphor is a natural element of language and one of the main tools that shape human thinking and communication. It states that this tool makes language more effective, understandable and creative.

Metaphor is reported to be a natural element of language, and it plays an important role in the system of human thinking and communication. The article highlights that modern linguistic studies show that this figure of speech is widely used not only as a literary stylistic device, but also in everyday speech, mass media and scientific writings. It shows its importance in the process of creating meaning in language and in the formation of human thinking.

Metaphor is also meant to be an integral part of creative strategies for creating meaning, especially in world languages such as English. This makes it necessary to study and research it, because its use is of great importance in terms of revealing hidden meanings in the text and correctly understanding the context.

Keywords: device, metaphor, meaning, types, structure, figurative

Metaphor, as a linguistic unit, is an effective linguistic device that creates new meanings by establishing a figurative connection between two different concepts or objects. Metaphor is known to be an important linguistic structure for thought and communication in English. This linguistic device creates new shades of meaning by metaphorically applying the properties of one concept to another concept, which ensures a better understanding of that concept. Metaphor is explained as "the expression of one concept in terms of another concept" and this process is a natural part of language. The main goal is to better explain one object or concept through another. According to the conceptual metaphor theory proposed by J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, metaphor is not only an aesthetic tool of language, but also a part of the human cognitive system. In their opinion, through metaphors, people shape their experiences by creating figurative connections and create complex meaning structures [11, p.46]. For example, the phrase "Life is a journey" embodies the main principle of this theory. Here, the concept of life is explained through the more concrete and structured term "journey", which creates a metaphorical connection to understand the different stages of life and the challenges encountered. According to J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, people tend to understand abstract concepts through such more concrete and recognizable experiences [11, p.53].

Metaphors occupy an important place in the structure of human thought in cognitive linguistics. According to the theory proposed by J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, abstract concepts in the human brain are explained by concrete experiences, and this is at the heart of the cognitive thinking system. According to this theory, metaphor through language reorganizes the thinking system and creates new connections between concepts.

As noted in J. Lakoff and M. Johnson's "Metaphors We Live By," conceptual metaphors are formed on the basis of human experience and help people understand their world. For example, the expression "time is money" describes time as a specific and limited resource, explaining the management of time in an economic sense [11, p.8]. Such metaphors change a person's view of the world and make abstract concepts concrete. Metaphor is considered to be one of the main tools of both poetic and descriptive language in literature. According to literary researchers, metaphor creates conditions for the creation of new meanings through "representing one object in the name of another object," which enriches the aesthetic side of language. For example, W. Shakespeare's famous phrase "All the world is a stage" emphasizes the metaphorical connection by comparing life to a theatrical stage [14]. This metaphor reflects the temporary and theatrical nature of human life, creating a new and deeper layer of meaning in the reader.

The effect of metaphor on perception is one of its most important functions. Through metaphor, people reorganize reality through the point of different concepts and renew their perceptions. Comparing an object or concept with another object or concept provides a new perspective on that object. For example, the phrase "love is war" shows that love relationships are full of conflicts and changes men's understanding of the relationship [14].

Researches in psychology and cognitive science show that metaphors play a key role in human understanding of abstract concepts and have a significant impact on perceptual processes [10, p.207]. Thus, the human brain perceives and structures figurative relationships more deeply based on concrete experiences. The

different use of metaphors from culture to culture reveals differences in their perception and worldview. Different cultures form metaphorical structures in different contexts, and this is reflected in their language and thinking. For example, the metaphor “time is money” is widespread in Western culture, but in some other cultures time is perceived more as a cyclical or fluid concept, and therefore metaphors are formed differently [12, p.178].

This is based on the different experiences that cultures have in metaphorical thinking and language systems, and people shape the conceptual structures of that culture through these metaphors.

Metaphors play an important role in the development and expansion of language. They expand the semantic field of language and create new layers of meaning in the description of various concepts. Along with the development of technology, new metaphors are created, and they are widely used in the language of technology in modern times. For example, the metaphor “cloud” was created to describe the concept of storing data over the internet, adding new layers of meaning to the language of technology. Such metaphors not only expand language, but also introduce new concepts to society through language [13, p. 90].

Thus, metaphor in English is not only considered to be an artistic and descriptive language tool, but also a central element of the human thought and perception system [9, p. 45]. Metaphors play an important role in the creation of meaning in language, in the organization of perception, and in the representation of culture. They facilitate perception by explaining abstract concepts in concrete, recognizable, and experience-based terms. Metaphor plays a key role in the development of language and human thinking, and influences the development of language as well as the thought process [8, p.40].

Metaphors play a fundamental role in both speech and thought in English. Through metaphors, people understand and interpret abstract concepts based on more concrete experiences. There are different types of metaphors, and each affects the structure of language and thinking in different ways.

We find it necessary to give some information about the main types of metaphors in English and their characteristics, examples, and detailed explanations based on scientific theories.

Conceptual metaphor is based on the conceptual metaphor theory of J. Lakoff and M. Johnson, and this type of metaphor occupies a central place in the system of human thought and experience. Conceptual metaphor ensures that an abstract concept is understood through a concrete concept. This idea is explained in detail in the work of J. Lakoff and M. Johnson “Metaphors We Live By”.

Conceptual metaphor is the representation of one concept by another concept, which ensures that people understand abstract thoughts with more concrete and familiar concepts. Conceptual metaphors organize human thought structures and thereby shape experiences in a conceptual framework. For example, the metaphor “Time is money” emphasizes the economic value of

time and allows people to understand their activities in life in the context of economic models [11, p.8].

These metaphors play a central role in everyday speech and our thought systems because they shape how we understand and interpret the world. Conceptual metaphors may take different forms in different cultures, but their function remains the same: to shape our thought systems by making abstract concepts more concrete and understandable. Each metaphor provides a way to relate a concrete concept to certain abstract concepts, making complex concepts such as emotions, time, and social relationships more easily understood. These types of metaphors provide people with deeper insights by relating the structure of one concept to the context of another.

Characteristics of conceptual metaphors can be defined as following:

- These metaphors structure human thought and frame experiences in a conceptual framework.

- The connection of abstract concepts, especially experiences such as emotions, time, life, and social relationships, with more concrete experiences.

- Conceptual metaphors are widespread in everyday language and speech, as people use these metaphors intuitively.

- Conceptual metaphors may appear in different forms in different cultures, but their function remains the same.

- Conceptual metaphors help people express their emotional and social experiences in a more concrete way.

- These metaphors structure language and influence how expressions in speech are formed.

Some examples of conceptual metaphors:

“Time is money” (Here, time is described as a resource, and this metaphor allows for the explanation of activities in life through economic models).

“Argument is war” (Debate is described as war, which emphasizes the winning and losing aspects of arguments) [1, s.4].

Structural metaphor is a subtype of conceptual metaphor, where one concept is structured by another. In this type of metaphor, we see that one concept is represented by another concept as a whole structure. Structural metaphor is a concept in which one concept is formed by the properties of another concept; it is a mechanism that people use to transform abstract concepts into a more concrete, understandable form. These metaphors allow abstract concepts (such as life, love, or time) to be explained in more concrete terms, which makes people’s experiences more understandable. Structural metaphors provide a framework that helps people understand their thought processes and daily lives; this allows them to simplify and understand complex concepts [3]. Structural metaphors organize the language structures that are essential for people to understand the world; thus, understanding the structure of language allows people to describe the world they think about more clearly. The widespread use of these metaphors also affects the development of people’s thought systems; because they create the basis for creating new concepts and reformulating old concepts [2].

Some features of structural metaphors:

- A concept is formed as a whole by the features of another concept.
- This usually provides an explanation of complex abstract concepts in simplified concrete terms.
- Structural metaphors make abstract concepts more understandable and comprehensible by relating them to concrete concepts.
- These metaphors provide a framework for guiding people's thought processes, thus helping to achieve better understanding in everyday life.
- Structural metaphors organize the structure of language and thought and help people understand the world.
- Structural metaphors provide new perspectives by allowing old concepts to be reformulated.

Examples of structural metaphors:

“Life is a journey” (The different stages of life are depicted as different parts of a journey, suggesting that experiences in life develop step by step) [11, s.44].

“Ideas are food” (Describing ideas as food), for example, like in the phrase “I can't digest that idea”.

An ontological metaphor is a type of metaphor in which abstract concepts are represented as objects, tangible entities, or substances. This approach helps people make intangible concepts more accessible and understandable. The main purpose of ontological metaphors is to objectify intangible concepts or to perceive them as entities. For example, the statement “the mind is a machine” presents thought processes as a mechanical structure.

These metaphors help people perceive complex and non-experienced concepts as simpler objects or entities. In the case of the statement “time is money”, it describes it as a tangible entity, giving it a concrete form. With the help of ontological metaphors, intangible concepts become more understandable in practice. In statements such as “love is a journey”, love, time, and other abstract concepts are depicted as journeys or tangible entities. Studies of how ontological metaphors shape language and thought show that these metaphors form the basis of human thinking and affect how we perceive the world.

An ontological metaphor is a type of metaphor that is used to help people perceive and imagine abstract concepts as objects and tangible entities. Through these metaphors, complex and abstract categories of thought are presented in the form of simpler and more concrete objects, which makes them easier to understand. This concept is explained in detail in the book “Metaphors We Live By” by C. Lakoff and M. Johnson.

Some characteristics of ontological metaphors:

The main feature of ontological metaphors is that abstract concepts are described as objects or tangible entities. This allows people to understand concepts in a more concrete and experience-based way. For example, the phrase “the mind is a container” is an example of an ontological metaphor. Here, the mind, while in fact a complex and abstract concept, is imagined as a container, which leads to its reduction to a more understandable form.

People understand more abstract and complex concepts based on the tangible objects they encounter

in their experiences. For example, the phrase “Time is money” is an example of this, where time is described as a tangible object. Here, time is presented as a resource that is spent or used. People can take control of abstract concepts by explaining the world with ontological metaphors. For example, metaphors such as “ideas are objects” allow ideas to be considered in a concrete way. In this way, people more easily assimilate and manage ideas.

Through ontological metaphors, people transform abstract concepts into tangible entities. For example, the expression “consciousness is a machine” associates the idea of the mechanism of consciousness with the image of a machine. This presents consciousness as a more controllable entity. Ontological metaphors are closely related to container metaphors. For example, the expression “The mind is a container” considers the mind as a specific object, showing that thoughts and feelings are stored in it. This metaphor brings people's feelings and thoughts into a more understandable form [3, p.25].

Abstract feelings and emotions are also presented through ontological metaphors. For example, the expression “Anger is a boiling liquid” depicts a person's anger as a liquid container, and this is imagined as a process in which the anger gradually fills up and finally bursts [4].

Examples:

“Mind is a container”: Here, the mind is considered as a container, and thoughts, memories, or information are placed inside it. This explains abstract concepts in a more objective and tangible way.

“Inflation is an entity”: Here, inflation is shown as an independent entity. For example, the phrase “inflation is eating up our savings” creates a description of inflation “eating up” savings as a living entity

Ontological metaphors help people understand complex and abstract concepts more easily. By shaping the structure of language and thought, these types of metaphors allow people to gain a greater sense of control over abstract concepts. The impact of ontological metaphors on both language and thought systems is one of the main topics of scientific debate and has an important role in understanding how language works and how it affects thought. As a result, ontological metaphors play an important role in people's understanding of the world and abstract concepts. They influence the formation of human thinking as a powerful tool of language and are widespread in culture [5].

There is a number of scientific literature that provides information about orientational metaphors. This type of metaphor is characterized by the association of abstract concepts with physical directions (up-down, in-out, front-back, etc.) [6].

The main essence of orientational metaphors:

Oriental metaphors are a type of metaphor that associates abstract concepts with physical spatial directions. These metaphors help people understand different emotions and experiences through certain directions. For example, “up” represents positive emotions, and “down” represents negative emotions. People apply the physical directions they experience

with their bodies to their thinking. For this reason, expressions such as “happiness is up” and “sadness is down” arise. Our bodily experiences guide our thinking and language [7].

Oriental metaphors relate emotions to space. For example, “up” represents positive feelings and states, while “down” represents negative or distressing states. Examples include “I’m feeling up today” or “He’s feeling down.” Control and management are also represented by orientational metaphors. For example, “control is up, and lack of control is down” are used to emphasize a person’s control over a situation. The phrase “He’s on top of the situation” is an example of this [8].

Difference between ontological and directional metaphors:

While ontological metaphors represent abstract concepts as objects, orientational metaphors are more related to physical spatial directions. Both types of metaphors help people understand abstract concepts, but orientational metaphors are specifically related to space. Oriental metaphors not only express emotions and experiences, but can also have different meanings in different cultures. For example, in some cultures, the metaphors of “right-left” also play an important role. Such metaphors can have different meanings in different societies.

Examples:

1. **“Happy is up, sad is down”** (Happiness is described as “up” and sadness as “down.” The phrase “I’m feeling up” means that a person is feeling good, while “I’m feeling down” means that a person is feeling bad).

2. **“Control is up, lack of control is down”** (Control is shown at the top, and lack of control is shown at the bottom. The phrase “He’s on top of things” means that a person is in complete control of a situation) [11, s.15].

3. **“More is up, less is down”** (This metaphor describes a greater quantity as being higher and a lesser quantity as being lower. For example, the phrase “Prices are going up” means that prices are increasing, while “His energy is low” means that his energy is decreasing).

Characteristics:

– Based on space and physical directions: Oriental metaphors are based on people’s bodies and spatial experiences. For example, people feel more energetic and good when they physically go up, which creates the metaphor “happiness is up.”

– Link abstract concepts to direction: These metaphors link abstract concepts (emotions, control, quantity, etc.) to spatial directions. This makes it easier for people to understand complex feelings and situations.

Polarization by direction: Positive concepts are usually associated with the direction “up,” while negative concepts are associated with the direction “down.” This creates a contrast in human thinking, such that those associated with “up” are good and those associated with “down” are bad.

Literary (poetic) metaphor is a language device widely used in works of fiction, poetry, and other

literary genres. It attempts to explain one concept in terms of the characteristics of the other by establishing a direct connection between two different concepts. The main purpose of literary metaphors is to make descriptions more powerful and emotional by going beyond the limits of ordinary language. These types of metaphors are used to create imagery, creative use of language, and deep meanings. Literary metaphors are a type of metaphor used mainly in works of fiction to create more impact and emotional depth. These metaphors aim for creative use of language, figurative expressions, and a more accurate conveyance of feelings. Literary metaphor is an effective type of metaphor used in works of fiction and literary genres such as poetry. These metaphors emphasize the aesthetic side of language and are more creative and figurative than ordinary communication.

The main purpose of literary metaphors is not only to explain a concept, but also to affect the feelings and thoughts of the reader. These types of metaphors attract the reader’s attention and increase the emotional charge of the work. For example, the expression “My heart is on fire” is not enough to simply explain an emotion, but also creates a strong image in the reader’s imagination. Literary metaphors are often symbolic and create ambiguous expressions that the reader can insert their own thoughts into instead of specific meanings. For example, the expression “Dark nights oppress my heart” is both metaphorical and symbolic, because darkness can represent a person’s distress in addition to being a concept directly related to darkness.

Literary metaphors create new and unique images that deviate from the ordinary use of language. Through these images, authors can evoke special scenes and feelings in the imagination of readers. For example, the phrase “Love is a lighthouse that finds its way by the stars” used in Shakespeare’s works is a figurative and unique metaphor. One of the important characteristics of literary metaphors is to create aesthetic appeal. In creative writing, metaphors are more complex and colorful than ordinary speech. Poets and writers create rhythm, harmony, and beauty in language through metaphors.

Examples:

1. “The world is a stage” [12, s. 15].

W. Shakespeare’s phrase “All the world’s a stage” is one of the most famous examples of this type. Here, life is likened to a theater stage and every person is shown as a performer.

2. “Hope is the thing with feathers” (Hope is depicted as a bird, flying with its wings to bring hope to people. This metaphor symbolizes that hope is fragile but strong).

3. “Shall I compare thee to a summer’s day?” (This metaphor, which compares a lover to a summer day, contains the idea of both beauty and transience).

Features of this metaphor:

– Imagery and creative thinking: Literary metaphors do not always give concrete and clear meanings. They create multi-layered meanings by using figurative expressions and affect the reader’s thinking. These metaphors encourage the reader to think and use their imagination.

– Subjectivity and expression of personal experiences: Literary metaphors are usually used to express the personal experiences and feelings of the author or characters. For this reason, they are also very subjective. For example, a poet may express his sadness and loneliness through images of nature such as the sea or the wind.

– Extensive use of language and literary techniques: Literary metaphors, combined with language techniques, strengthen the structure of the writing. In works of fiction, such metaphors affect the overall flow of the work rhythmically and aesthetically. This feature is more pronounced in genres such as poetry.

– Complex and ambiguous approaches: Literary metaphors are often complex and multilayered. They allow for poetic expression of feelings and situations that are difficult to explain in simple language, which adds ambiguity to literary works.

CONCLUSION

Metaphors are an integral part of human thinking and language comprehension. Metaphors allow us to explain abstract concepts through concrete images and influence a person's perception of the world.

Metonymy increases the efficiency of communication and serves to express ideas more concisely and accurately. Through metonymy, one concept is replaced by another based on proximity or connection, thereby ensuring density of meaning.

Metaphors not only enrich the artistic style of language, but also act as one of the main structural elements of thought and the system of meaning. According to the theory of conceptual metaphor, metaphors play an important role in human understanding of the world and help to figuratively establish connections between experiences.

Different types of metaphors - conceptual, structural, ontological and directional metaphors - perform specific functions in different styles of language and systems of meaning.

Conceptual metaphors help people better understand abstract concepts.

Structural metaphors increase the perceptual power of language by explaining one concept in terms of the properties of another concept.

Ontological metaphors make intangible concepts more understandable by likening them to concrete objects.

Directional metaphors, on the other hand, draw on human bodily experiences to connect emotional and physical states with spatial directions.

Metaphors act as one of the main organizers in the structure of the text. Metaphors shape the structure of

the text, determining its conceptual framework and meaning system. Metaphors enhance the emotional and stylistic characteristics of the text, making it more effective and memorable. They are also widely used in scientific, academic and journalistic texts. In particular, the role of metaphors is indispensable in explaining new concepts and presenting concepts in a more understandable form.

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